

New Records of Myxomycetes from Shenandoah National Park

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Received: 28 April 2026

Accepted for publication: 17 May 2026

Published: 20 May 2026

Editor: Carlos Rojas

Abstract: A list is provided of species of myxomycetes recorded from Shenandoah National Park in Virginia as a result of surveys carried out during 2025. The species reported are based on specimens that developed in the field under natural conditions and also specimens that appeared in moist chamber cultures. Fifteen species representing 13 genera are reported as new from the park. This brings the number of genera and the number of species known from the park to 36 and 94, respectively. These numbers do not represent the total number of species likely to occur in the park, which can only be determined by intensive sampling over an extended period of time.

Keywords: biodiversity, moist chamber cultures, slime molds, temperate forests

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Introduction

Stephenson and Stephenson (2025) provided a checklist of all the species of myxomycetes reported from or known to occur in Shenandoah National Park in the Blue Ridge Mountains of Virginia. The majority of these species (87% of the 79 species in the checklist) were the result of surveys carried out during 2024. These surveys considered both specimens that had fruited under natural conditions in the field and specimens that were recorded from moist chamber cultures. The purpose of this paper is to report the results of additional surveys carried out during 2025.

Materials and methods

In the present study, all specimens of fruiting bodies collected in the field along with samples of bark, ground litter, aerial litter, and woody twigs were collected from areas adjacent to the Skyline Drive. This highway extends through the entire park and over most of its length is flanked by relatively xeric oak-hickory forests (Fig. 1). For the field surveys, all substrates upon which the fruiting bodies of myxomycetes might be expected to occur were examined in an opportunistic manner as described by Cannon and Sutton (2004). When fruiting bodies were observed, they were collected along with the portion of the substrate upon which fruiting had occurred. All samples of the various types of plant material were returned to the laboratory and used to prepare moist chamber cultures in the manner described by Stephenson and Stempen (1994).

Figure 1. Oak-hickory forest along the side of the Skyland Drive as viewed in spring before full foliage has developed (Photo by Steve Stephenson).

When fruiting bodies were observed in the moist chamber cultures, they were removed along with the piece of the substrate upon which fruiting had occurred. These were dried at room temperature. Afterwards, pieces of the substrates with fruiting bodies present were glued to paper trays and the latter placed in small pasteboard boxes for permanent storage. The same method used for specimens collected in the field. All specimens of myxomycetes are deposited in the herbarium (JMUH) of James Madison University.

Results

A total of 120 specimens were recorded during 2025. Most of these could be identified to the level of species, but a few were too aberrant for this to be possible. These specimens represented 15 species in 13 genera new to Shenandoah National Park.

Annotated List of Species

In the list that follows, all species of myxomycetes recorded as new for Shenandoah National Park are arranged alphabetically by genus and then species. Information is provided on the source(s) of the record. The nomenclature used follows Lado (2005-2025) except where noted. Recent molecular studies have resulted in a number of taxonomic rearrangements in the myxomycetes. As a result, some familiar species now have names that would not be immediately recognized by many of the people who collect and study myxomycetes. Numbers given in parentheses are the collecting numbers of the first coauthor.

Comatricha reticulospora Ing & P.C. Holland

Represented by one specimen (SNP-355) appearing in a moist chamber culture on twigs of white pine (*Pinus strobus*).

Comatricha rigida (Brândza) G. Moreno, A. Sánchez & A. Castillo

Represented by one specimen (SNP-352) appearing in a moist chamber culture on bark from red cedar (*Juniperus virginiana*).

Cribraria intricata Schrad.

Represented by two specimens (SNP-292 and SNP-300) collected in the field from decaying logs of red spruce (*Picea rubens*).

Cribraria vulgaris Schrad.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-271) collected in the field from a decaying pine log of pitch pine (*Picea rigida*).

Diderma testaceum (Schrad.) Pers.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-257) appearing in a moist chamber culture of leaf litter.

Didymium iridis (Ditmar) Fr.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-335) collected in the field from a piece of dead bark.

Fuligo septica (L.) F.H. Wigg.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-309) collected in the field from a decaying log.

Hemitrichia leiotricha (Lister) G. Lister

Represented by one specimen (SNP-231) appearing in a moist chamber culture on twigs of an unidentified tree.

Hemitrichia pardina (Minakata) Ing

Represented by one specimen (SNP-245) appearing in a moist chamber culture on bark from red cedar (*Juniperus virginiana*).

Licea bulbosa Nann.-Bremek. & Y. Yamam.

Represented by two specimens (SNP-251 and SNP-274) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs of balsam fir (*Abies balsamea*).

Lycogala exiguum Morgan

Represented by one specimen (SNP-331) appearing in the field from decaying wood of an unidentified tree.

Nannengaella leucopus (Link) J.M. García-Martín, J.C. Zamora & Lado

Represented by one specimen (SNP-310) collected in the field from bark covered with mosses. In all but the most recent treatments of the myxomycetes, this species is listed as *Physarum leucopus* Link.

Nannengaella mellea (Berk. & Broome) J.M. García-Martín, J.C. Zamora & Lado

Represented by one specimen (SNP-283) that fruited in a culture prepared with a plasmodium collected in the field. In all but the most recent treatments of the myxomycetes, this species is listed as *Physarum melleum* (Berk. & Broome) Masee.

Perichaena corticalis (Batsch) Rostaf.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-229) appearing in a moist chamber culture on bark of white oak (*Quercus alba*).

Stemonitis flavogenita E. Jahn

Represented by one specimen (SNP-290) collected in the field on dead wood from an unidentified tree.

The 15 species recorded as new for Shenandoah National Park bring the number of genera and the number of species now known from the park to 36 and 94, respectively. It is anticipated that additional surveys carried out in the future will yield even more species for the park.

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